

Exploring The Factors That Influence Students' Behavioralintention To Use M-Learning

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>Mobile learning (m-learning) applications have recently become a phenomenon, and there is increasing demand for their incorporation into the educational sector. However, many educational institutes face challenges among their student bodies in both the acceptance and use of m-learning applications. The aim of this study is to examine the essential factors that may affect students' behavioral intention to use these applications, specifically employing the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model to determine the influence of different factors on students' adoption and usage of m-learning applications. Data were collected via online questionnaire, to which 290 university students responded. Results showed that effort expectancy and performance expectancy were significant factors that determined student acceptance and use of m-learning applications, while facilitating condition and social influence were insignificant, having no effect on students' behavioral intention toward the usage of m-learning applications. The results of this study provide essential information for educational institutions as to how they can increase students' utilization of m-learning applications. Some implications of m-learning acceptance and usage were discussed.</i></p>
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Introduction

Mobile learning (m-learning) applications have, of late, become an essential tool for both instructors and students (Almaiah, 2018). These applications are capable of supporting quick access to learning content and information regardless of place, time, and manner, thus creating a new opportunity for the delivery and innovation of learning services management (Hamidi and Jahanshaheefard, 2019). M-learning is one of the recently emerging tools that can be used to enhance learning and teaching performance for both students and instructors; it assists in providing activities, learning materials, and services for students in real time by utilizing mobile devices such as smartphones (Pimmer et al., 2012). Even though several universities have taken the crucial step of pursuing m-learning initiatives, the provision of learning services that employ mobile technologies is now becoming an inevitable part of the educational landscape (Criollo-C et al., 2018). Current mobile service providers and researchers do not have a clear understanding of learners' needs and requirements during the course of mobile device use. Moreover, there are still technical challenges and other issues associated with the adoption of m-learning (Alshammari et al., 2016; Kumar and Chand, 2019; Al-Emran et al., 2018), specifically with regard to its acceptance and usage by students (Almaiah et al., 2016; Alshammari, 2020). Because such adoption and acceptance is vital to ensuring the successful utilization of m-learning systems in the context of education, it is essential to identify and understand the crucial factors that may affect how students come to accept—or reject—this mode of learning. While a limited number of studies examined the acceptance of m-learning (Al-Shihi, 2018; Al-Emran et al., 2018), they did not determine all of the crucial factors involved. Furthermore, the majority of IS models and theories, and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) in particular, have rarely been extensively examined and tested within a non-Western educational context, such as developing Arab countries (El-Masri and Tarhini, 2017; Alalwan et al., 2015). The current study attempts to fill that gap by applying UTAUT in order to examine the main determinants of students' acceptance of m-learning applications in the educational context.

Literature review

Lately, several colleges and universities have transitioned to offering services and learning activities via m-learning applications (Almaiah, 2018). By enhancing the delivery of learning content and materials in this way, students are not only afforded greater opportunities for timely and location-free access to curricular materials, they are provided with an extra channel for interacting with their instructors (Hamidi and Jahanshaheefard, 2019). In addition, as part of a new kind of information system interface, m-learning applications facilitate a number of administrative and educational services, such as uploading and downloading learning materials, submitting assignments, viewing information offered by instructors, and paying fees, to name a few. Thus,

universities must ensure that the m-learning applications they use not only encourage student acceptance and adoption of these methods, but also meet and satisfy learners' requirements through high-quality, interactive services (Pimmer et al., 2012).

As already mentioned, m-learning applications offer tremendous benefits to instructors, students, and employees: greater accessibility to and availability of educational information and materials via smartphones or other devices, fast instructor-student interaction and conveyance of information, and practical assistance in academic administrative functions. However, despite the provision of m-learning application in universities, the rate of acceptance and adoption among the student population is still low (Almaiah et al., 2016). Such limitation gives focus to the present study, which aims to examine the essential factors that motivate and determine the adoption and use of m-learning applications among students in the education context.

In the literature related to information systems (IS), the adoption and acceptance of any technology is vital for ensuring the success of its implementation. Thus, it is essential to examine and identify the factors that may influence students' use of m-learning systems. Several investigations (e.g., Almaiah et al., 2016; Al-Emran et al., 2018; Kumar and Chand, 2019) have stated that a primary issue in studying the acceptance of m-learning applications lies in how mobile service providers and current researchers do not have a clear picture about the needs and requirements of students in this regard. In order to solve this problem, several researchers (e.g., Almaiah et al., 2016; Al-Shihi et al., 2018; Aburub and Alnawas, 2019; Sánchez-Prieto et al., 2019) have examined the determinant factors possibly affecting m-learning application use and acceptance by applying several different acceptance models such as TRA, TAM, TBP, and others.

Based on the literature, several models and theories have been utilized to examine users' adoption and acceptance of new emerging technologies. For instance, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was designed by Davis et al. (1989), followed by TAM2 by Venkatesh et al. (2003), TBP by Ajzen (1991), and TRA by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). Each of these models and theories was utilized, developed, and validated by several researchers in order to gain clearer insights and to determine the factors that could affect technology use and acceptance (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Comparative studies using these different models have also been conducted in order to choose the most convenient theory and models for examining and predicting technology adoption and acceptance (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Alshammari, 2020). These studies found out that UTAUT had the higher explanatory power when compared to the other theories and models of IS acceptance. According to Al-Mamary et al. (2015), the UTAUT model is the most famous in the context of technology adoption, and it focuses on the influencing factors for a successful implementation of technologies. Several studies have reported similar results; for example, Sana'a (2016) mentioned that the UTAUT model is considered one of the commonly known models that predicts the adoption and utilization of technology among users. In addition, Walldén et al. (2016) conducted a meta-analysis review of 69 published studies, and concluded that the UTAUT was a robust and valid model due to the substantial evidence of these empirical studies.

According to several other studies, UTAUT was confirmed as a robust and valid model for explaining users' acceptance and adoption of new technologies in many different contexts (e.g., Abdullah and Ward, 2016). Furthermore, the UTAUT model has begun to receive greater attention among researchers compared to other models such as TAM, TAM2, TRA, and TBP (Abubakar and Ahmad, 2013), given its higher explanatory power and higher efficiency (Taherdoost, 2018). However, the UTAUT model has been rarely examined and explored within a non-Western context, especially in an educational context such as developing Arab countries (El-Masri and Tarhini, 2017; Alalwan et al., 2015; Alshammari, 2021). With these considerations in mind, the researcher selected UTAUT as the optimal model to examine the factors that could affect students' adoption and usage of m-learning applications.

Research Model:

As mentioned previously, to ensure the successful implementation of m-learning applications in the educational context, the factors that may affect the usage, acceptance, and adoption of m-learning systems should be taken in account and examined (Delone and McLean, 2003; Alshammari, 2020).

PERFORMANCE EXPECTANCY (PE)

PE is known as the extent to which a specific technology can benefit the user once they are performing a specific activity (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The construct of PE is commonly included in UTAUT for predicting the behavioral intention toward using ICT systems (Venkatesh et al., 2012). For instance, Sung et al. (2015) applied the UTAUT model in their examination of IS usage in South Korea, and their results indicated that PE influenced behavioral intention. The results of similar studies by Kaliisa et al. (2019), Nikolopoulou (2018), and Botero et al. (2018) also showed that PE was a determinant of behavioral intention toward technology use. Thus, it is proposed in this study that:

H1: Performance Expectancy has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications.

EFFORT EXPECTANCY (EE)

EE is defined as the level of efforts that is required for performing a specific task (Venkatesh et al., 2012). It is a vital construct in the UTAUT model, and is applied extensively in order to examine users' behavioral intention toward using a new technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Sung et al. (2015) found that effort expectancy was an influencing factor that determines the acceptance and usage of m-learning in South Korea. Several similar research studies, such as those by Almaiah and Al Mulhem (2019), Nikolopoulou (2018), and Botero et al. (2019), utilized the UTAUT model and found out that effort expectancy had a positive significant effect on behavioral intention toward using a technology. Thus, the hypothesis is formulated as:

H2: Effort Expectancy has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications.

SOCIAL INFLUENCE (SI)

SI is known as the extent to which users think other people think that they ought to be utilizing a technology (Venkatesh et al., 2012). It is the third construct in the UTAUT model. While some studies have shown that it could be quite a determinant of and influential factor on behavioral intention toward the usage of technology, others have indicated that there is no relationship between social influence and behavioral intention. Kaliisa et al. (2019) found out that social influence was a significant influential factor on mobile learning acceptance, while Joo et al. (2014) found out that there was no strong relationship between social influence on users' behavioral intention and usage of m-learning acceptance in South Korea. It is possible that such variance depends on the context of the different countries' cultures. Thus, the hypothesis of this study is formulated as:

H3: Social Influence has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications.

FACILITATING CONDITIONS (FCs)

FCs are known as the perception of users of the available support and resources once they are performing a specific task (Venkatesh et al., 2012), and they constitute a vital construct in the UTAUT model. More specifically, Venkatesh et al. (2003) found that facilitating conditions were a significant factor that determines users' behavioral intention and usage. In addition, several other studies examined the relationships between the facilitating condition construct and the adoption and acceptance of online government services. For instance, Sung et al. (2015) used the UTAUT model for exploring the adoption of m-learning services, and found that the facilitating condition was a determinant factor influencing the acceptance and adoption of m-learning systems. Thus, the hypothesis of the proposed model is formulated as:

H4: Facilitating Condition has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications.

BEHAVIORAL INTENTION (BI)

BI is known as the willingness toward using a selected technology (Ajzen, 1991). Based on the study of Venkatesh et al. (2003), BI was a significant determinant of the usage of technology. Moreover, several previous studies showed that BI had a positive effect on the usage of technology (Al-Adwan et al., 2018; Abu-Al-Aish and Love, 2013; Sultana et al., 2020; Alshammari, 2020; Alshammari, 2021). Thus, the hypothesis of these constructs is formulated as:

H5: Behavioral intention has a significant positive effect on students' actual usage of m-learning applications.

The proposed research model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research model

Methodology

Participants:

The targeted participants of this study were undergraduate students in the College of Education at the University of Ha'il. The students were enrolled in different departments such as psychology, sport science and physical activity, and Islamic culture, and were currently using m-learning systems to participate in lectures and engage in learning activities using a blackboard. The participants could thus assist in achieving the objective of this research: to obtain a better understanding of, and more details about, which factors could affect the adoption and use of m-learning applications, specifically from their point-of-view.

Data collection method:

A quantitative approach was applied in this study using a questionnaire survey. Data collection was performed during the second semester 2020/2021 by distributing an online, self-administrated survey among students in the College of Education at the University of Ha'il. Overall, 400 questionnaires were distributed to students; 290 questionnaires were included for analysis, with a response rate of 72.5%. The sample size of this study (n=290) is convenient and acceptable. According to Loehlin (1992), at least 100 cases, or preferably 200 cases, are required for statistical SEM analysis; furthermore, Hair et al. (2010) suggested at least 10 cases per dependent variable. Based on this, it was determined that the proposed model of the present study would consist of six constructs.

Instrument development:

The survey included two parts: the first focused on measuring demographic information such as gender, age, and use of m-learning applications for educational purposes, while the second was an adopted and modified item for measuring the factors in the proposed model. The adapted items measure all factors in the proposed model such as effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating condition, and social influence, which were adapted from a study of Venkatesh et al. (2003), while the behavioral intention toward the use of technology and actual use were adapted from a study of Venkatesh et al. (2012). The questionnaires applied a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 5 for "strongly agree" to 1 for "strongly disagree." The Likert five-point scale is known to be more accurate when compared to a three-point scale (McCoach and Adelson, 2010).

Evaluation of the research model:

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was applied to examine the relationships among six constructs in the model. The two steps in SEM analysis were applied: in the first step, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to measure model fitness as well as construct, convergent, and discriminant validity; in the second, SEM was applied to analyze the path and test the proposed hypothesis in the structural model.

Results

Part1: Respondents' demographic information analysis

A total of 320 undergraduate students participated the survey. However, only 290 surveys were considered for further analysis because of invalid and incomplete responses. Table 1 presents information regarding respondents such as gender, age, and use of m-learning applications for educational purposes. In summary, 185 students (63.8%) were male, and 105 students (36.2%) were female; most were 21–23 years of age (180 students, or 62.1%), followed by those 18–20 years of age (54 students, or 18.6%) or older than 26 years of age (10 students, or 3.4%); and the majority use m-learning applications (192 students, or 66.2%), while some do not (98 students, or 33.8%).

Table1

Respondents' Descriptive Information

Characteristics	N	%
Gender		
Male	185	63.8
Female	105	36.2
Age (years)		
18-20	54	18.6
21-23	180	62.1
24-26	46	15.9
More than 26	10	3.4
Total	290	100.0
Using Mobility for learning		
YES	192	66.2
NO	98	33.8
Total	290	100.0

Part2: Applying CFA and SEM

According to Hair et al. (2010), conducting a pooled CFA is considered to be the best method to validate model measurement due to its ability to handle different construct correlations and errors of measurement. It could also address a number of constructs in the same analysis. Moreover, it could assist in avoiding identification issues due to the fewer number of items measuring the constructs in the model (Awang, 2015). During the CFA run, the measurement model needed to be assessed and developed by assessing its construct validity as well as discriminant and convergent validity (Awang, 2015). Thus, the construct validity of the model was assessed. In addition, fitness indices were assessed and achieved the suggested level after eliminating some of the items with loading factors such as SI4, SI5, FC3, FC4, AU1, AU2, and AU5. The pooled CFA results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Pooled CFA

Awang (2015) stated that construct validity is met once the fitness of the model achieves the suggested level established by prior studies. The model fitness results in Table 2 below indicate that the model fitness values achieved the suggested level, which means that the construct validity was met.

Table 2

Model Fitness

Name of category	Name of index	Index value	Level of acceptance	Decision
Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.077	<0.08	Achieved the suggested level
	CFI	0.938	0.90>	Achieved the suggested level
Incremental fit	TLI	0.926	0.90>	Achieved the suggested level
	NFI	0.906	0.90>	Achieved the suggested level
Parsimonious fit	Chisq/df	2.703	<3.0	Achieved the suggested level

After assessing the construct validity, the convergent and discriminant validity need to be checked before testing and analyzing the path for the hypothesis. According to Hair et al. (2010) and Awang (2015), the convergent validity is met once the AVE value exceeds 0.05 for all constructs in the model and the CR value exceeds 0.60. The results of CR and AVE analysis presented in Table 3 below show that they achieved the suggested level. Thus, the convergent validity was achieved.

Table 3

CR and AVE

	CR	AVE
BI	0.964	0.843
PE	0.903	0.655
EE	0.900	0.693
SI	0.825	0.612
FC	0.769	0.629
AU	0.732	0.582

Finally, the discriminant validity has to be examined to make sure that all constructs in the model are discriminant from each other. The bold value in the table is a square root of AVE for the construct, while the other values are the correlation between the model constructs. According to Awang (2015), the discriminant validity is met when the BOLD values are higher than the other values in its rows and column. Therefore, the results presented in Table 4 below confirm that the discriminant validity of all model constructs is achieved.

Table 4

Discriminant Validity

	BI	PE	EE	SI	FC	AU
BI	0.918					
PE	0.741	0.849				
EE	0.654	0.657	0.833			
SI	0.482	0.509	0.590	0.782		
FC	0.559	0.552	0.828	0.571	0.857	
AU	0.790	0.833	0.786	0.553	0.701	0.842

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

SEM: Standardized Estimate

SEM analysis outputs two types of results: standardized and unstandardized estimates. The standardized estimate is utilized for assessing the beta coefficient among constructs, factor loading of items into the construct, and R².

The unstandardized estimate, on the other hand, is a beta estimate, and it is essential for calculating the critical ratio in order to test the hypothesis. Figure 3 shows the first run for the standardized estimate.

Figure 3: Standardized estimate

The R² of the AU construct is 0.64, which explains that 64% of the Actual Use factor is explained by the construct of behavioral intention. The R² of BI is 0.62, which means that 62% of the BI construct is explained by the exogenous constructs in the model such as PE, EE, SI, and FC. The results show that the model has a high explanatory power in explaining students' behavioral intention and their actual use of m-learning applications. According to Falk and Miller (1992), the R² value has to be equal to or greater than 0.10 in order to be considered adequate. Choen (1988) stated that an R² value of 0.12 or less means a low explanatory power, while a value between 0.13 to 0.25 means a medium explanatory power, and any value above that means a high explanatory power of the model. Based on that suggestion, since the R² of this model is 0.64, this means that the proposed model has a high explanatory power for explaining students' acceptance and usage of m-learning applications.

SEM: Unstandardized Estimate

The unstandardized estimate is also essential for understanding the regression weight (beta estimate) and also for calculating the critical ratio to test the research hypothesis. Figure 4 presents the unstandardized estimate for the model.

Figure 4: Unstandardized estimate

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Table 5 presents the Regression Weights between the constructs in the model: Table 6 presents the results of hypothesis testing.

Table 5

Regression Weights

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
BI <--- PE	.470	.055	8.587	***	Significant
BI <--- EE	.253	.105	2.420	.016	Significant
BI <--- SI	.057	.080	.711	.477	Not Significant
BI <--- FC	.047	.122	.390	.697	Not Significant
AU <--- BI	.600	.066	9.145	***	Significant

Table 6

Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Results
H1: Performance Expectancy has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications	Supported
H2: Effort Expectancy has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications	Supported
H3: Social Influence has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications	Not Supported
H4: Facilitating condition has a significant positive effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications	Not Supported
H5: Behavioral intention has a significant positive effect on students' actual usage of m-learning applications	Supported

Discussion

The findings confirmed that effort expectancy and performance expectancy both had a significant effect on students' behavioral intention and usage of m-learning applications. Surprisingly, the other two external factors—namely, facilitating conditions and social influence—were insignificant and had no influence on students' behavioral intention and use of m-learning applications.

Starting with performance expectancy, PE was found to have a positive significant effect on students' behavioral intention to use m-learning applications; this is in line with the finding of the original theoretical UTAUT model (Kumar and Chand, 2019). The results imply that once students find m-learning applications useful, their behavioral intention toward using them increases.

The results also revealed that effort expectancy had a positive significant effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications; this supports the finding of the original UTAUT model (Kumar and Chand, 2019). The results imply that when students find m-learning applications easy to use, simple, and user friendly, their behavioral intention toward the usage of m-learning applications increases.

Regarding the social influence factor, the results showed it to be insignificant, with no effect on students' behavioral intention toward the usage of m-learning applications. Although this is in line with prior studies (Sultana, 2020; Buabeng-Andoh and Baah, 2019; Alshammari, 2021), the result is opposite that of the original hypothesis in the UTAUT model (Kumar and Chand, 2019). The explanation, as it concerns the current investigation, is that when students find m-learning applications useful and easy to use (performance expectancy

and effort expectancy), they do not require any input from their peers and are not influenced by them. This thought is claimed by Venkatesh et al. (2003), who found that when the factors of PE and EE are significant, social influence and facilitating condition are deemed to be insignificant.

In terms of facilitating condition, the results showed it to be an insignificant factor in influencing students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications. Surprisingly, this finding contradicts with the original study of Venkatesh et al. (2003); however, it is in line with some previous studies (Alshehri et al., 2019; Sultana, 2020). A possible explanation of this finding is that most students nowadays know how to access and manage technology at anytime and from any location. Thus, they are not in need of a FC, but rather are more focused on how technology is useful (performance expectancy) and easy to use (effort expectancy). Consequently, FC was an insignificant factor concerning students' behavioral intention toward using m-learning applications.

Finally, behavioral intention was also revealed to have a positive significant influence on students' actual use of m-learning applications. That finding is in line with most prior studies (Alshehri et al., 2019; Sultana, 2020; Lewis et al., 2013; Venkatesh et al., 2003). This finding implies that when students have an intention to use m-learning applications, then their behavioral intention will lead to the actual usage of m-learning applications.

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

This research provides some essential, practical insights into the adoption and acceptance of m-learning applications among students, particularly the determinant factors in this regard. These insights can, in turn, assist designers, policy makers, researchers, and developers by increasing their knowledge of, and familiarity with, students' preferences in regards to the key factors influencing students' acceptance and use of m-learning applications.

First, the key external factors in the UTAUT model influencing user behavioral intention toward the usage of technology in developed countries are not necessarily influencing factors in developing countries due to different contexts, cultures, and other factors. In this study, for instance, even though performance expectancy and effort expectancy were significant factors concerning students' behavioral intention toward using m-learning applications, which is in line with the original UTAUT model, the other external factors such as social influence and facilitating condition were insignificant and had no influence on students' use of m-learning applications. Thus, policy makers in the same context and culture should focus on the influencing factors that may impact students' behavioral intention toward using m-learning applications, which, in turn, will increase their usage as well as their value in student learning performance.

Furthermore, the study findings can assist developers and designers in identifying students' needs and requirements prior to implementing the m-learning applications intended for their use. This study shows that performance expectancy and effort expectancy are significant factors that affect students' behavior toward the usage of m-learning applications. Accordingly, m-learning application systems must be helpful and easy to use, and taking into consideration students' prior comments and opinions about system utility and ease of use can advance overall use.

Researchers can also benefit from this study. The two external factors; namely, facilitating condition and social influence—were insignificant constructs and had no effect on students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning application. This result contradicts with the original UTAUT model, which might be due to cultural differences and context. Other researchers could conduct similar studies in other Arab contexts to determine whether their results are in line with the original UTAUT model or are different in light of variations in context and culture.

Conclusion

This study utilized the UTAUT model to examine and explain the determinant factors that affect students' acceptance of m-learning applications. Thus, the determinant factors that influence students' behavioral intention toward the use of m-learning applications were identified. The study results showed that performance expectancy and effort expectancy were the contributing factors influencing students' acceptance of m-learning applications, whereas the other external factors—namely, facilitating condition and social influence—were insignificant and did not have an influence on students' acceptance of m-learning applications.

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